

AESOP

Alert-Early System of Outbreaks
with Pandemic Potential

USE AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS, MODELS AND TOOLS AVAILABLE IN THE DASHBOARDS OF AESOP

AESOP: Early Warning System for Outbreaks with Pandemic Potential

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Funding

The Rockefeller Foundation

Use and Interpretation of the Results, Models and Tools Available in AESOP Dashboards

ISBN 978-65-01-46413-8

C972x Cunha, Gerson, 1963 -
Use and Interpretation of the Results, Models and Tools Available in AESOP
Dashboards / Gerson Cunha. -- 1. ed. -- Rio de Janeiro, RJ : Ed. do Autor, 2025.

15p, Inclui índice
ISBN 978-65-01-46413-8

1. Technology. 2. Aesop. 3. Pandemic. 4. Influenza. I. Título. II. Cunha, Gerson. III.
Cunha, Maria Célia. IV. Marconso, Fábio. V. de Oliveira, Juliane. VI. Miranda, Ray.

CDD - 372.358

SUMÁRIO

Objective of this manual	04
General objective of the dashboards	04
Benefits of using our dashboards	05
Target audience	06
Available Dashboards	06
Requirements for Use	07
Access to Dashboards	07
Technology Used	08
Maintenance and Updates	08
Support and Error Reporting	08
Step-by-Step Guide to Navigating and Using the Strategic Dashboard	09
Suggestions for Analyzing and Interpreting Data in the Strategic Dashboard	11
Step-by-Step Guide to Navigating and Using the Technical Dashboard	12
Suggestions for Analyzing and Interpreting Data in the Analytical Technical Dashboard	14
Step-by-Step Guide to Navigating and Using the Metagenomic Dashboard	15
Step-by-Step Guide to Navigating and Using the Socioeconomic Dashboard	17
Step-by-Step Guide to Navigating and Using the Climate Dashboard	18
Step-by-Step Guide to Navigating and Using the Web-based Dashboard	20
Main Interface Elements	22
Buttons and Checkboxes	22
Resume/Summaries	23
Maps	24
Graphs	25
Tables	25
Team	26

OBJECTIVE OF THIS MANUAL

This manual has been prepared to guide users in the use and interpretation of the results, models and tools available in the visualization dashboards.

GENERAL OBJECTIVE OF THE DASHBOARDS

The dashboards were developed with the purpose of facilitating the early detection of outbreaks with pandemic potential, in addition to offering valuable insights for quick and effective decision-making.

The AESOP project provides a set of interactive dashboards designed to:

a. **Identify**, in an agile manner, **the presence or absence of weekly warnings** at the municipal level, **which indicate** possible **anomalies** in the monitoring of **Influenza-Like Illness (ILI) Encounters** in Primary Health Care (PHC).

b. **Allow** users **to contextualize and correlate** detected warnings with **different sources** of information, such as:

- i. Drug sales data;
- ii. Web search trends;
- iii. Socioeconomic indicators;
- iv. Climate conditions;
- v. Human mobility patterns.

These features enable more in-depth analysis and assist in the validation and reliability of identified warnings, contributing to a more efficient response to potential outbreaks.

BENEFITS OF USING OUR DASHBOARDS

1

Early and sensitive detection: Identify outbreaks and potential emergencies of unknown pathogens with high accuracy, enabling a rapid and effective response.

2

Intelligent contextualization of warnings: Access strategic information that helps contextualize and potentially validate outbreak warnings, increasing the reliability of the analysis.

3

Support for the collection of genomic samples: Optimize the collection of genomic samples based on an integrated approach, which considers human mobility; presence of indigenous populations; deprivation index; population density and signals detected in Primary Health Care (PHC). This ensures a better understanding of the spread of pathogens and improves surveillance strategies.

4

Facilitated decision-making: Use dynamic insights to support strategic decisions and optimize control and prevention actions.

5

Impact mitigation: Contribute to reducing the impact of the emergence of new pathogens and communicable diseases, protecting communities and strengthening public health

TARGET AUDIENCE

Our dashboards are designed to present results in a clear and intuitive way, ensuring that any user, regardless of their level of technical knowledge, can easily interpret the information. The simplified interface allows for practical access to data, optimizing decision-making.

Given their purpose of early detection of outbreaks, the dashboards are especially useful for:

- Health professionals;
- Laboratory technicians;
- Researchers;
- Epidemiological surveillance program managers.

AVAILABLE DASHBOARDS

Strategic dashboard

Presents a summary view, allowing the user to quickly identify the presence or absence of warnings in the region of interest.

Technical dashboard

Provides a broader set of information, facilitating the validation and contextualization of detected signals.

Metagenomics dashboard

It identifies priority locations for the collection of genomic samples. This prototype integrates weekly PHC notices with patterns of intermunicipal human mobility, deprivation index, population density and data from Special Indigenous Health Districts (DSEI). The integration of these data is essential to identify areas with the greatest potential for early detection of pathogens, in addition to highlighting regions that are most vulnerable to misidentification and the spread of diseases.

Socioeconomic dashboard

Displays the relationship between the number of calls and the occurrence of warnings, considering the distribution of these occurrences in areas with different levels of deprivation.

Climate dashboard

Allows us to explore the association between climate events and the emergence of new services, helping to understand the possible influence of climate on the occurrence of Influenza-Like Illness (ILI).

Web-based dashboard

A dashboard designed to monitor searches for terms related to Influenza-Like Illness (ILI). It allows exploring the association between the frequency of internet searches for terms related to Influenza-Like Illness and possible epidemiological trends.

REQUIREMENTS FOR USE

Necessary Equipment

- Computer or mobile device with internet access.

Accesses

- Sign consent form
- Login and password provided by the administrator.

Compatible Software

- Supported browsers: Google Chrome, Mozilla Firefox, Safari.

ACCESS TO DASHBOARDS

1. Access the link: <https://aesop.outerlamce.com>

2. Enter your access credentials (username and password) provided by the administrator (see support section).

3. Click “Login” to access the main interface.

Troubleshooting

- If you are unable to access the site, check your internet connection.
- Contact technical support if the problem persists

TECHNOLOGY USED

The dashboards are built using **open-source technologies**, ensuring transparency, flexibility, and reproducibility. The interface uses **React**, a widely adopted JavaScript library, combined with **Bootstrap** for responsive design. Visualizations are built with **Chart.js** for dynamic charts and **Leaflet** for interactive maps, both open-source and compatible with React.

The backend uses **MySQL** for efficient storage and a **Laravel API** for automated data access and updating. Using these open tools makes it easier for other researchers and institutions to replicate the dashboards, promoting the scalability and accessibility of the solution..

MAINTENANCE AND UPDATES

Data is updated weekly. The date of the last update can be found at the bottom of each dashboard page. Some datasets may be updated at different times of the week: most data is updated on Wednesdays; drug sales data may be updated on Fridays.

SUPPORT AND BUG REPORTING

If you need any support or for technical questions, problems or inconsistencies in the data, please contact the system administrator by email: aesop@fiocruz.br.

STEP-BY-STEP GUIDE TO NAVIGATING AND USING THE STRATEGIC DASHBOARD

1 Painel Técnico | **Painel Estratégico**

2 Semana Epidemiológica: 12-2025

3 Estado: Todos | Município: Todos

4 Sinal AESOP: Aviso, Sem Aviso, Não Apto

5 Total de Sinais: 262 | **Provável Síndrome Gripal na APS: 239872** | Total de Atendimento na APS: 4.829M

5 Probabilidade de crescimento | **Provável Síndrome Gripal na APS**

Consulta dos Indicadores nos Municípios

UF	Município	Provável Síndrome Gripal	Atendimentos Totais	DQI
RN	São Fernando	39	256	Apto
SC	Brunópolis	22	290	Apto
SC	Governador Celso Ramos	323	1949	Apto
SC	Santa Terezinha	62	555	Apto
RS	Bom Retiro do Sul	84	1321	Apto
RS	Condor	80	983	Apto
RS	Entre Rios do Sul	53	570	Apto
RS	Gaurama	86	474	Apto
RS	Parei Novo	32	263	Apto
RS	Progresso	63	559	Apto
RS	São Borja	387	3773	Apto
RS	Sarandi	242	2014	Apto

Atualizado em 27/03/2025

- 1 Access the strategic dashboard** by selecting the corresponding option in the main menu.
- 2 Check the epidemiological week** indicated on the dashboard, which represents the reference period for the data display.
- 3 Select the state and municipality** of interest using the available filters to view information specific to your region.
- 4 Check the status of your municipality's warning** given by monitoring the PHC series and the series of drug sales counts (OTC).
- 5 Follow trends in ILI Encounters in PHC**, view a **summary with the number** of encounters and monitored signs and access the complete **table** with information from all municipalities, facilitating comparison with other regions of interest.

SUGGESTION OF ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA IN THE STRATEGIC DASHBOARD

Scenario 1: Signals from Multiple Sources

- PHC: Signal present
- Sale of Medicines: Signal present
- Probability of Growth: High (greater than or equal to 80%)
- Proportion of Care for Influenza-Like Illness (ILI): High (compared to the last year)
- Border Municipalities: Also present a signal

Interpretation: There is a strong indication of an increase in cases in the municipality, possibly reflecting an ongoing outbreak. The presence of signs in neighboring municipalities suggests regional spread.

Scenario 2: Signal in the PHC, but not in the Sale of Medicines

- PHC: Signal present
- Sale of Medicines: No signal
- Probability of Growth: Moderate (between 60% and 80%)
- Proportion of Care for Influenza-Like Illness (ILI): Moderate (compared to the last year)
- Border Municipalities: No signal

Interpretation: An increase in the number of encounters may indicate a localized situation, with no immediate impact on medication consumption. Additional monitoring is recommended.

Scenario 3: Signal in the Sale of Medicines, but not in the PHC

- PHC: No signal
- Sale of Medications (OTC): Signal present
- Probability of Growth: Low (compared to the last year)
- Proportion of Care for Influenza-Like Illness (ILI): Low (less than 60%)
- Border Municipalities: No signal

Interpretation: Increased drug purchases may be an early indicator of future growth in care. Monitoring in the coming weeks is essential.

Scenario 4: No signal on monitored sources

- PHC: No signal
- Sale of Medicines: No signal
- Probability of Growth: Low
- Proportion of Care for Influenza-Like Illness (ILI): Low
- Border Municipalities: No signal

Interpretation: The municipality appears to be in a period of stability, with no signs of a significant increase in cases.

Scenario 5: Scattered signals and moderate growth

- PHC: No signal
- Sale of Medicines: No signal
- Probability of Growth: Moderate
- Proportion of Care for Influenza-Like Illness (ILI): Moderate
- Border Municipalities: Some show signal

Interpretation: The scenario suggests a gradual increase in cases, possibly at an early stage. Continuous monitoring is necessary to detect possible growth trends.

STEP-BY-STEP GUIDE TO NAVIGATING AND USING THE TECHNICAL DASHBOARD

AESOP Monitoramento dos Atendimentos por Provável Síndrome Gripal na Atenção Primária em Saúde (APS) no Brasil

2 Painel Técnico | Painel Estratégico

Semana Epidemiológica: 12-2025

Estado: Todos | Município: Todos | Sinal de Aviso: Sinal AESOP | DQI: Apto | Probabilidade de Crescimento: <math> < 75 < /math> | <math> > 75 < /math> e <math> < 85 < /math> | <math> > 85 < /math> | MIP: Aviso

1 **1** **3**

Probabilidade de Crescimento: -%
 Provável Síndrome Gripal na APS: 239872
 Total de Atendimentos na APS: 4.829M
 Excesso de Provável Síndrome Gripal: -%
 Total de Sinais: 1032

Semana Epidemiológica: 12-2024 a 12-2025

Proporção de Provável Síndrome Gripal

4 **4**

Semana Epidemiológica 12
 Média Móvel: 5.73 %
 Proporção (Provável Síndrome Gripal / Total de atendimentos): 4.97 %

Provável Síndrome Gripal na APS

4 **4**

Semana Epidemiológica 12
 239872
 Provável Síndrome Gripal na APS

Total de Atendimentos na APS

4 **4**

Semana Epidemiológica 12
 4.829M
 Total de Atendimentos na APS

Semana Epidemiológica: 12-2025

Estado: Todos | Município: Todos | Sinal de Aviso: Sinal AESOP | DQI: Apto | Probabilidade de Crescimento: <math> < 75 < /math> | <math> > 75 < /math> e <math> < 85 < /math> | <math> > 85 < /math> | MIP: Aviso

Consulta dos Indicadores nos Municípios

UF	Município	Provável Síndrome Gripal	Atendimentos Totais	Proporção de Provável Síndrome Gripal	DQI	Completação (%)	Tempestividade (%)	Probabilidade de Crescimento (%)	Sinal AESOP Consecutivo	Limite Sinal AESOP	Excesso Sinal AESOP (%)
RN	São Fernando	39	256	15.23	Apto	100.00	99.96	100.00	1	36	1.7
SC	Brunópolis	22	290	7.59	Apto	100.00	95.21	100.00	1	18	1.18
SC	Governador Celso Ramos	323	1949	16.57	Apto	100.00	94.74	100.00	0	336	0
SC	Santa Terezinha	62	555	11.17	Apto	100.00	100.00	100.00	1	37	1.40
RS	Bom Retiro do Sul	84	1321	6.36	Apto	100.00	99.73	100.00	1	54	1.35
RS	Condor	80	983	8.14	Apto	100.00	98.36	100.00	1	60	1.25
RS	Entre Rios do Sul	53	570	9.30	Apto	100.00	100.00	100.00	1	33	1.37
RS	Gaurama	86	474	18.14	Apto	100.00	100.00	100.00	1	62	1.27
RS	Pareci Novo	32	263	12.17	Apto	100.00	100.00	100.00	1	23	1.28
RS	Progresso	63	559	11.27	Apto	100.00	99.13	100.00	1	37	1.41

1 Check the detailed warning status of your municipality. In addition to the **“Warning”** and **“NoWarning”** options, the dashboard also indicates whether the municipality has had a warning signal (weak red) for more than one consecutive week or is in a situation of attention (yellow).

2 Use the new filters

2.1 Monitor the warning issued by different detection models.

2.2 Identify municipalities without sufficient data quality for analysis (classified as “Not suitable”).

2.3 Select different growth probability levels.

2.4 Enable the OTC (drug sales) advisory layer to cross-reference information.

Attention: The drug sales signs layer is only visible when selecting a state in the “State” filter.

3 Check counts and estimates for your municipality

3.1 Consult information on the proportion of encounters due to probable Influenza-Like Illness (ILI) in relation to the total number of encounters.

3.2 Analyze the probability of growth and excess of identified cases.

4 Follow the trends in ILI Encounters in PHC

4.1 Visualize time series, moving averages and the service ratio series.

4.2 Access the complete table with information on all municipalities, facilitating comparison with other regions of interest.

SUGGESTION FOR ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA IN THE COMPLETE DASHBOARD

Scenario 1: Consistent alert and multiple warning signs

- PHC data quality: Suitable, with consistent records.
- PHC: Municipality presents consecutive signal.
- Drug sales: There is a signal in the sale of drugs.
- Coincidence of signals: The signal in the sale of drugs coincides with the consecutive signal in the PHC.
- Proportion of excesses: Relevant.
- Trend: Evidence of seasonality or beginning of a local outbreak.

Interpretation: The combination of multiple signs suggests a real increase in demand for care, reinforcing the need for continuous monitoring and possible preventive action.

Scenario 2: Signal on drug sales, but no alert on PHC

- PHC data quality: Suitable.
- PHC: No sign or state of attention.
- Medication sales: Sign present.
- Coincidence of signs: No correlation with signs in the PHC in the current week.
- Proportion of excesses: As expected.
- Trend: No significant variations in the proportion of services, low probability of growth.

Interpretation: This may indicate an increase in the perception of flu-like symptoms by the population before seeking medical care. It is recommended that the data be monitored in the coming weeks to see if there will be an impact on the PHC.

Scenario 3: No warning on AESOP sign, but other models and drug sales indicate warning

- Data quality: Suitable.
- PHC: No signal in AESOP, but other models show alert.
- Sales of medicines: Signal present.
- Signal coincidence: Yes, strong overlap with other detection models.
- Proportion of excesses: Above expected (according to the model's estimate indicating a warning).
- Probability of growth: High (greater than or equal to 80%)
- Trend: Possible onset of seasonality or localized increase.

Interpretation: The absence of a warning in AESOP may indicate that the model methodology did not capture this emerging behavior. As other signals point to possible growth, it is recommended to intensify surveillance and check the data in the coming days.

STEP-BY-STEP GUIDE TO NAVIGATING AND USING THE METAGENOMICS DASHBOARD

AESOP Locais Estratégicos para Coleta de Amostras Metagenômicas

1 **Gripe** **Arbo**

Metagenômica **Painel Resumido**

Estado: Todos **4** Município: Todos **4** Critérios de Ordenação dos Municípios: Mobilidade, Densidade, IBP, DSEI **3**

Semana Epidemiológica 12-2025

Semana Epidemiológica 12-2025

Lista das Cidades com Maior Potencial para Detecção Precoce de Patógenos

UF	Município	Ordenação	DQI	Sinal AESOP
São Paulo	São Paulo	1	Não Apto	0
Rio Grande do Sul	Porto Alegre	2	Não Apto	0
Ceará	Fortaleza	3	Não Apto	0
Paraná	Curitiba	4	Não Apto	0
Bahia	Araci	5	Apto	0
São Paulo	São Caetano do Sul	6	Não Apto	0
Pernambuco	Recife	7	Apto	1
Maranhão	Itapecuru Mirim	8	Apto	0
Maranhão	Santa Rita	9	Não Apto	0
Ceará	Ipueiras	10	Apto	0
Alagoas	Batalha	11	Apto	0
Roraima	Iracema	12	Apto	1
Maranhão	Vitória do Mearim	13	Não Apto	0

2

Cidades de Origem dos Avisos na APS e Municípios Destino Recomendados para Coleta Genômica

Origem		Destino	
UF	Município	UF	Município
Alagoas	Belo Monte	Alagoas	Arapiraca
Alagoas	Belo Monte	Alagoas	Batalha
Alagoas	Joaquim Gomes	Pernambuco	Cabo de Santo Agostinho
Alagoas	Joaquim Gomes	Pernambuco	Escada
Alagoas	Joaquim Gomes	Pernambuco	Palmares
Alagoas	Joaquim Gomes	Pernambuco	Recife
Alagoas	Joaquim Gomes	Pernambuco	Ribeirão
Alagoas	Joaquim Gomes	Pernambuco	Xexéu
Alagoas	Joaquim Gomes	Alagoas	Colônia Leopoldina
Alagoas	Joaquim Gomes	Alagoas	Maceió
Bahia	Amargosa	Bahia	Brejões

5

Atualizado em 27/03/2025

1 Access the metagenomics dashboard. In the main menu, select the corresponding option to view the information.

2 Identify the municipalities indicated for the collection of genomic samples. On the map and in the first available table, check the municipalities suggested for collection. The order of the municipalities is determined by the **Municipal mobility coverage criteria, population density, socioeconomic conditions** (measured by the Brazilian Deprivation Index - IBP), presence in indigenous health district - DSEI. Check the table to see if the suggested municipality is in a warning situation and if the quality of the PHC data in the current week is satisfactory.

3 Adjust the criteria for selecting municipalities. Use the available filters to modify the selection criteria according to your local needs.

4 Refine search by state. Apply filters to view only the ordering of municipalities in a specific state.

5 On the map (when selecting a state) and in the second table, **identify the place of origin of the virus** that may have spread or been responsible for the **signal** detected two weeks ago **in the municipality indicated for collection.**

STEP-BY-STEP GUIDE TO NAVIGATING AND USING THE SOCIOECONOMIC DASHBOARD

1 Access the socioeconomic dashboard. In the main menu, select the corresponding option to view the information.

2 Analyze the distribution of warnings by level of deprivation. Consult the map to identify regions with different levels of the Brazilian Deprivation Index. Check the count of municipalities that have warnings in relation to the category defined by the index.

3 Explore the detailed information in the table. Access data on the number of warnings, total number of encounters and encounters due to probable Influenza-Like Illness (ILI). Analyze the proportion of encounters by deprivation category to understand the relationship between socioeconomic vulnerability and the alerts issued.

STEP-BY-STEP GUIDE TO NAVIGATING AND USING THE CLIMATE DASHBOARD

1 Grife Arbo

2 Map of Bahia, Brazil, showing temperature anomalies and AESOP signals (Warning, Attention, Not Applicable).

3 Weekly summary for Week 12 (Semana Epidemiológica 12):

- Temperatura Média Semanal °C: 27.45 °C
- Precipitação Total Corrigida mm: 2.81 mm
- Umidade Relativa do Ar %: 2.10 %

1 Access the climate dashboard. In the main menu, select the corresponding option to view the information.

2 Analyze the spatial distribution of warnings. On the map, observe the distribution of warnings in different climate zones, characterized by monthly variations in temperature, humidity and precipitation in relation to the average, in the same period, corresponding to previous years. Identify which climate characterization your municipality is in and what its warning status is.

3 Explore the detailed information in the graphs. Analyze the trends in primary health care encounters in conjunction with variations in temperature, humidity, and precipitation. Use this information to better understand the relationship between climate factors and care patterns.

STEP-BY-STEP GUIDE TO NAVIGATING AND USING THE WEB-BASED DASHBOARD

The screenshot displays the AESOP dashboard interface. At the top, the logo and name 'AESOP' are visible, along with the text 'Eventos de Interesse na Web'. Navigation tabs for 'Gripe' and 'Arbo' are present, with 'Gripe' selected. Below this, a menu shows 'Web Based' and 'Painel Resumido', with 'Painel Resumido' highlighted. A green circle with the number '1' is placed over the 'Painel Resumido' tab.

The main content area is titled 'Google Trends' and shows data for 'Semana Epidemiológica: 04-2024 a 04-2025'. It includes dropdown menus for 'Estado' (set to 'Todos') and 'Município' (set to 'Todos'). The primary chart, 'Proporção de Provável Síndrome Gripal vs Termos', is a dual-axis line graph. The left y-axis represents 'Provável Síndrome Gripal na APS' (0 to 800,000), and the right y-axis represents 'Termos' (0 to 100). The x-axis shows dates from 04-2024 to 04-2025. A red line tracks the probable influenza syndrome, while various colored lines represent different symptoms. A green circle with the number '2' is placed over the main chart area.

To the right of the chart is a legend for 'Semana Epidemiológica 4' with a list of terms: Coriza, Covid, Diarreia, Dor de Cabeça, Dor de Garganta, Falta de Ar, Febre, Gripe, Resfriado, Tosse, and Vômito. Each term has a checked box next to it.

Below the main chart, there are controls for 'Variável' (set to 'Coriza') and 'Média Móvel' (set to '1 Semana'). The secondary chart, 'Proporção de Provável Síndrome Gripal vs Termos vs Termos Média Móvel', is a dual-axis line graph showing the same data as the main chart but with a smoothed red line for the probable influenza syndrome. A green circle with the number '3' is placed over this chart area.

To the right of the secondary chart, a summary box for 'Semana Epidemiológica 4' displays the following statistics:

- 128706** Provável Síndrome Gripal na APS
- 50.00 %** Coriza
- 50.00 %** Média Móvel Coriza

1 Access the web-based dashboard. In the main menu, select the corresponding option to view the information.

2 Analyze the relationship between consultations and searches for terms. Observe the trend in ILI Encounters and the search for different terms on Google Trends. Check if there is an association between the increase in searches for certain terms and the trend in consultations in your city. Use the filter box to select the terms of interest.

Attention: The search series represent aggregated data for the entire state.

3 Explore individual trends and the weekly summary. Analyze separately the evolution of services and searches for specific terms. Consult the summary of the current week for a consolidated view of the results presented.

MAIN INTERFACE ELEMENTS

The main elements defined so far are:

- Buttons and checkboxes
- Resume / Summaries
- Maps
- Graphs
- Tables

BUTTONS AND CHECKBOXES

Located at the top of the dashboard, before the maps, graphs and tables, are interactive tools for customizing the data visualization. These elements allow the user to define the period and geographic area of interest, as well as allow adjustments to display different results or data layers (warning models, growth probability categories, etc.) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Buttons and checkboxes. (A) Set of elements that allow the customization of information visualization. The main components include the identification of the epidemiological week (in week-year format), the corresponding date range, the temporal scroll bar, as well as checkboxes for state, municipality and variables relevant to the analysis of the selected region (type of signal, data quality indicator, probability of growth and signal in drug sales). (B) Checkboxes available in the genomic dashboard, allowing the customization of the choice of municipalities for the collection of genomic samples based on different criteria. (C) Term selection format in the web-based dashboard, allowing the selection of keywords for specific analysis.

RESUME / SUMMARIES

These are dialog boxes that display key metrics that summarize the current situation of the selected geographic region. This information can highlight relevant data or complement the dashboard analysis. To do this, we use different visual resources, such as dialog boxes, icons and images, which help to contextualize the indicators presented (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Different forms of information summaries available in the dashboards.

MAPS

Each dashboard displays a map with an initial layer that presents an overview of the country at the municipal level, highlighting the mapped variable. The different layers allow you to explore the situation at different levels of management — municipal, state and federal. When you select a state, the map highlights its municipalities, providing a more detailed view. In addition, when you hover over a municipality, a dialog box displays a strategic of its situation, facilitating a quick and contextualized analysis of the data.

Figure 3: Maps representing different information in the developed dashboards. (A) Distribution of Brazilian municipalities according to the warning status, as presented in the technical dashboard. (B) Identification of priority municipalities for the collection of genomic samples. (C) Regionalization of municipalities based on their deprivation index.

GRAPHS

While maps represent information spatially, graphs organize data temporally, allowing analysis of evolution or variation over time. Different graphic formats can be used in a dashboard, and are chosen based on the best way to communicate the available content. The user's familiarity with these formats is also considered, as poorly selected graphs can make data interpretation difficult (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Some of the main types of graphs used in dashboards. Bar graph: Represents data in bars proportional to the measured values, allowing comparisons between discrete categories (in this case, dates). Line graph: Used to show trends over time by connecting sequential data points. Area graph: Suitable for displaying cumulative data series or relationships between parts and the whole.

TABLES

Tables complement the other dashboard elements by providing details about the original data. They can include both the variables used in the charts and other additional information available for analysis.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The visualization team would like to thank all the AESOP project participants and collaborators who contributed to the development of this work. We would especially like to thank the institutions involved for the support and infrastructure provided, as well as the technical and scientific teams who participated in the improvement of the dashboards and analyses.

Our recognition also extends to the health professionals and researchers who provided important insights, helping to validate and apply the results. Institutional support and collaborative work were essential to make this project viable and strengthen health surveillance.

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